

1 **Toxic elements identified in breast milk of mothers residing in water contaminated region**
2 **of Sindh and their impact on infants' growth patterns: A case-control study**

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28 **Abstract**

29 Breast milk is a vital source of nutrition for breastfed infants, providing essential nutrients and
30 elements but, in some cases, toxic ones. This is the first case-control study that investigated the
31 elemental profile of breast milk samples collected from mothers residing in Matiari (Sindh), a
32 region with insufficient industrial waste management, and its potential impact on infants'
33 anthropometrics. Precisely, 62 milk samples, including 42 cases and 20 controls, were analyzed
34 using the ICP-MS technique. Overall, six elements showed significance between the two
35 groups, arsenic (As) was present at 0.68 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in cases and absent in controls, while lead (Pb)
36 exhibited elevated concentrations in the case group at 4.56 $\mu\text{g/L}$ compared to 0.25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in
37 controls, well-known for their toxicity. Barium (Ba) and manganese (Mn) levels were also
38 higher in cases, associated with reported health effects on child well-being. Essential elements
39 molybdenum (Mo) and selenium (Se) were higher in the controls. Furthermore, the association
40 of these metals with the child growth standards as per WHO guidelines was calculated. Linear
41 regression analysis revealed As negatively associated with WAZ and WHZ scores, while Mo
42 was positively associated with WAZ, WHZ, and HAZ scores. These findings highlight serious
43 health concerns in the region, where toxic elements pervade drinking water and food sources.
44 Immediate actions are imperative to maintain the wellness of future generations.

45 **Keywords:** Breast milk; toxic elements; weight-for-age z score (WAZ); weight-for-height z
46 score (WHZ); height-for-age z score (HAZ); infant health.

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53 **1. Introduction**

54 Indeed, breast milk is nature's perfect food as it has all the nutrients required in an infant's early
55 infancy. It provides essential elements such as nutrients, vitamins, and minerals along with
56 non-nutritional components like immunologic and antimicrobial factors which are crucial
57 contributors to advancement in an infant's growth. The presence of these elements lowers the
58 chances of infant mortality and morbidity [1]. Nevertheless, over time, the concentrations of
59 micronutrients in breast milk may be significantly impacted by the mother's dietary practices,
60 variations in dietary patterns, and environmental exposures [2]. Micronutrient deficiencies in
61 human milk or infant formula during early life have negative implications for infants,
62 correlating with short-term infections and increased disease rates. Conversely, excessive levels
63 of micronutrients can also pose harm [3].

64 Breast milk can pass environmental toxins from the mother's environment, such as metals and
65 organic compounds, to the baby [4], so it is obvious that both mother-infant pairs are vulnerable
66 to the negative effects of toxic metals. The susceptibility of newborns to toxic metals, including
67 Pb, Cd, and As, is a critical concern due to their widespread presence and detrimental effects
68 on infants' nervous systems [5]. Even at low concentrations and with acute exposures, infants
69 are susceptible to harm from exogenous xenobiotics, as their liver detoxification enzymes are
70 less proficient than those in adults. These early exposures can lead to lasting cognitive deficits
71 throughout life [6].

72 Heavy metals contribute to environmental and atmospheric pollution, posing potential harm to
73 human health. Their toxicity intensifies when interacting with elements like water, soil, and
74 air, exposing humans and other organisms through the food chain [7]. In a study on water
75 quality in Sindh, Pakistan, Rind et al. found 18–70% of groundwater samples exceeding WHO
76 limits for heavy metals (Ni, Cr, Pb, Cd, As, and fluoride), emphasizing significant health risks
77 and the potential transfer of these contaminants into the food chain [8].

78 There is still debate over the ideal daily intake of the necessary trace elements such as Ca, Mg,
79 Mn, Se, and Zn. It is evident, though, that their inadequate consumption may stunt growth,
80 result in anemia, have an impact on the immune system, and be harmful to other organs'
81 function. On the other hand, toxicity could result from an intake that is far higher than the
82 necessary dose [9, 10]. Meticulous determination of the mineral content of human breast milk
83 is crucial for high-risk infants, such as preterm, underweight, and infants with inborn
84 abnormalities [11].

85 One of the most widely employed techniques for determining the elemental composition of
86 materials is inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). In previous studies,
87 levels of toxic elements in human milk samples were found to exceed the recommended limits
88 set by the World Health Organization (WHO) [12-14]. In addition, Li *et.al.* discovered that
89 mineral intake, including Ca, Mg, K, Na, and Se consistently fell below the adequate intake
90 recommended by the Institute of Medicine across all three lactation stages [15].

91 To date, there has been a paucity of studies investigating the elemental composition of breast
92 milk and its influence on the growth patterns (Weight-for-Age z score, WAZ; Weight-for-
93 Height z score, WHZ; and Height-for-Age z score, HAZ) of breastfed infants in the Matiari
94 (Sindh) region of Pakistan. This study aims to fill this gap by conducting a comprehensive
95 analysis of both toxic and essential elements present in breast milk, comparing distinct case
96 and control groups. Through our research, we seek to elucidate the associations between these
97 elemental compositions and the growth patterns observed in infants.

98 **2. Materials and methods**

99 **2.1. Milk Sample Collection**

100 A total of 62 breast milk samples were collected from mothers in the nursing stage, i.e. between
101 3-6 months in the rural area of Matiari, Sindh, Pakistan. The Department of Pediatrics and
102 Child Health at Aga Khan University approved the conducted study, and all subjects including

103 healthy individuals provided their informed consent. The ethics committee approval number
104 (ICCBS/IEC-065-HB-HM-2021/Protocol/1.0I) was taken from the International Center for
105 Chemical and Biological Sciences Ethics Committee.

106 Out of 62 samples, 42 were mothers of undernourished children, categorized as the case group,
107 while the remaining 20 were mothers of well-nourished children, denoted as the control group.
108 The inclusion criteria specified the mothers whose children were aged between 3-6 months.
109 For the case group $WHZ < -2$ was required, while healthy controls had a $WHZ > 0$ and HAZ
110 > -1 within the same age range. Mothers with children having metabolic diseases were not
111 included in this study. Specifically, metabolic diseases such as diabetes, hyperlipidemia and
112 other congenital metabolic disorders were not included in our participant selection criteria.
113 Detailed clinical parameters, including maternal weight, age, BMI, infant gestational age
114 gender, and z-scores (HAZ , WAZ , WHZ) along with other important biomarkers were also
115 observed during the sample collection period.

116 **2.2. Reagents and instrumentation**

117 Nitric acid (HNO_3) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) used for sample digestion were purchased
118 from (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Ultra-pure deionized water ($\approx 18.2 M\Omega \cdot cm$) was used to
119 prepare all solutions from the Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA). Trace element
120 analysis was performed with a Thermo Elemental X7 Series inductively coupled plasma-mass
121 spectrometry (ICP-MS) system coupled with with Cetac ASX-510HS high-speed auto sampler
122 (Omaha, Nebraska 68144 USA). Multi-element calibration standard 2A (catalog no. 8500-
123 6940) was purchased from Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA) to prepare the
124 standard solutions for the calibration curve. Microwave-assisted digestion systems (Anton
125 Paar, Graz, Austria) equipped with a 64 MG 5 rotor were used for sample digestion for ICP-
126 MS analysis.

127 **2.3. Sample preparation and ICP-MS analysis**

128 0.5 mL of milk samples were taken directly into the Teflon vessels. Then 1.5 mL of 65 %
129 HNO₃ and 0.25 mL of 35 % H₂O₂ were added and dissolved in the microwave. The already
130 reported protocol was used for sample preparation with some minor changes [6]. The following
131 parameters were set for the microwave-assisted digestion: maximum power of 1000 W, a ramp
132 duration of 15 min to reach 200 °C, and then a holding period of 20 min at the temperature of
133 200 °C. The vessels were then allowed to cool at room temperature for 30 minutes after
134 completing the digestion process.

135 With ultra-pure water, extracted solutions were diluted to a volume of 12.5 mL. Throughout
136 the entire analysis, the blank sample was likewise prepared in the same manner. A standard
137 curve was created using a series of verified multi-element standard concentrations of 10, 25,
138 50, 100, and 250 ppb were prepared to produce calibration curves for all analytes.

139 ICP-MS was used for the analysis of the prepared samples. The instrument utilized an octopole-
140 based collision/reaction cell (ORS3) with helium as the inert gas. The sample introduction
141 employed a low-flow concentric nebulizer paired with a Scott-type double-pass spray chamber
142 (Agilent Technologies). Between analyses, sample washout was ensured using two rinsing
143 solutions: 2% nitric acid and 0.5% hydrochloric acid. Each sample underwent an individual
144 examination.

145 **2.4. Data processing and statistical analysis**

146 Multivariate analysis was performed by using MetaboAnalyst 6.0. [16]. Data were normalized
147 by median and data scaling was conducted (via Pareto scaling) mean-centered and then divided
148 by the square root of the standard deviation of the variable to make features more comparable
149 in magnitude to each other. Subsequently, Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed
150 to extract the underlying patterns and relationships among the concentrations of toxic and
151 essential elements in breast milk samples from malnourished and healthy infants aged between

152 3 and 6 months. By reducing the dimensionality of the data, PCA facilitates the identification
153 of key factors driving differences or similarities in elemental composition between the two
154 groups of infants. Cross-validation of the PLS-DA model was executed through a five-fold
155 cross-validation method, and its quality was evaluated based on R² and Q² scores. The R²
156 value characterizes variation across the model and fitness, determined by the number of
157 components within the model. Meanwhile, Q² is used to assess the overall predictive capability
158 of the model, independent of the data used for model training. Additionally, permutation tests
159 (n = 1000) were employed to validate the model and mitigate any overfitting in the PLS-DA
160 model. Univariate analysis of potential distinct marker elements was carried out using the
161 unpaired t-test with a predefined threshold for the false discovery rate (FDR) corrected p-value
162 of 0.05, and the fold change (FC) threshold was set at 2. The resulting volcano plot can be
163 visualized in Supplementary Fig. S1. Linear regression analysis was also performed with IBM
164 SPSS Software (version 21, Chicago, IL, USA) to examine the associations between identified
165 metals and children's z-scores, adjusting for birth weight, gestational age, and age at the time
166 of sample collection.

167 **2.5. Hierarchical clustering and random forest classification**

168 Cluster analysis was employed to categorize breast milk samples into clusters based on
169 similarities in elemental composition. This allows for the identification of subgroups or clusters
170 of breast milk samples with similar toxic and essential element profiles.

171 In the hierarchical clustering analysis, distances were measured using Pearson's algorithm,
172 followed by the implementation of the Ward clustering algorithm. The results, presented as a
173 dendrogram and heat map, showcased the outcomes of the HCA. Moreover, the Random Forest
174 (RF) classification method (Supplementary Fig. S2) was employed for predicting future
175 instances using multiple classifiers, thereby improving accuracy and reliability. It also provides

176 valuable insights, including the estimation of out-of-bag (OOB) errors and the identification of
177 outliers Supplementary Fig. S3.

178 **3. Results**

179 **3.1. Characteristics of the study population**

180 The detailed clinical characteristics presented in Table 1 offer valuable insights into essential
181 anthropometric measures for both mothers and their breastfed infants within the case-control
182 study. Notably, the calculated p-values across various parameters highlight the statistical
183 significance of these findings. The comparison between the case and control groups regarding
184 parameters such as HAZ, WAZ, and WHZ, which are indicative of malnutrition, was as
185 anticipated, confirming the suitability of the comparison groups for the study's objectives. Key
186 differences in anthropometric measures, particularly z-scores such as HAZ, WAZ, and WHZ,
187 are summarized here, with further detailed comparisons available in Table 1. Moreover,
188 significant differences were observed between the two groups regarding gestational age, birth
189 weight, and age at the time of sample collection. These variables were adjusted in the analysis
190 to account for their potential confounding effects on the studied anthropometric parameters.
191 While gender distribution was consistent across both groups, the control cohort displayed
192 superior anthropometrics compared to the case group. Exploring the biomarker profile at six
193 months further clarifies distinctions between both groups, with elevated levels of growth-
194 related markers like IGF1 and leptin observed predominantly in the control group.
195 Additionally, rota irus vaccine status is presented as the number of responders who have taken
196 the vaccine.

197 **3.2. Elementomics profile of breast milk**

198 Overall 62 milk samples, comprising 42 cases and 20 controls were analyzed using ICP-MS.
199 Among the examined elements, arsenic (As), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), barium (Ba),
200 selenium (Se), and molybdenum (Mo) emerged as significant differentiators between the two

201 distinct groups. Elevated levels of As, Pb, Mn, and Ba were observed in the case group,
202 indicating a potential association with specific health conditions within this cohort. In contrast,
203 the control group exhibited higher concentrations of Se and Mo.

204 **3.2.1. Univariate analysis for significant elements between two groups**

205 Univariate analysis was conducted to identify elements in breast milk that significantly differ
206 between the case and control groups. Using a t-test, with a FC > 2 and an FDR corrected *p*-
207 value < 0.05, six elements were identified as significant contributors distinguishing between
208 the two groups, as presented in Table 2. Notably, As showed the most substantial increase in
209 the case group (FC = 18.917, *p* = 0.002), while Pb also exhibited a notable elevation (FC =
210 2.889, *p* = 0.036). Fig. 3 displays the box plot of these elements along with their normalized
211 intensities.

212 **3.2.2. Multivariate analysis for discrimination between samples**

213 PCA was conducted on the concentration values of various elements to gain an overview of
214 the dataset and obtain patterns from the intricate experimental results. The unsupervised PCA
215 analysis, based on ICP-MS data of all samples showed the overall structure of the dataset.
216 Specifically, the first two principal components (PCs) collectively accounted for 51.4% of the
217 overall variance. PC1 contributing 36.4%, demonstrates a higher compatibility with the cases,
218 while PC2 representing 15% of the total variability, exhibits a greater compatibility with the
219 controls, respectively. As shown in Fig. 1A, the PCA scores plot displayed a clear separation
220 between the case and control group. The scree plot displayed in Fig. 1B indicates that the initial
221 five principal components collectively account for 76.2% of the variance present in the data.
222 Subsequently, discriminant analysis based on elemental concentrations was conducted to
223 categorize groups. Through, supervised PLS-DA, specific combinations of the original
224 variables were found that accurately determined group classifications and captured a significant
225 part of the variation in the elemental profile of milk samples. Graphical representation

226 illustrated in 2D score plot (Fig. 2A). Reliability of the constructed PLS-DA model and its
227 predictive capability, a five-fold cross-validation method was employed as shown in Fig. 2B.
228 The results, with $R^2 = 0.677$ and $Q^2 = 0.584$, and accuracy = 0.902, indicate overall good
229 performance of the model. Additionally, to confirm the statistical validity of these predictive
230 models, permutation tests were carried out 100 times, as illustrated in Fig. 2C with a p-value
231 of less than 0.01.

232 **3.2.3. Cluster analysis and classification modeling**

233 A heatmap and dendrogram were generated through hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA). The
234 HCA was visualized using a dendrogram, as depicted in Fig. 4A, effectively grouping the case
235 and control groups. The clustering represented in the heatmap displayed intensity values within
236 each colored cell, arranging samples in rows and attributes in columns. The axes of the
237 heatmap, as illustrated in Fig. 4B, were determined based on the results of the t-test.

238 Furthermore, a random forest classification was employed due to its enhanced robustness
239 against overfitting and outlier misclassification. This approach builds numerous decision trees
240 and integrates them to improve predictive accuracy. During the training phase, the RF
241 algorithm incorporates cross-validation using out-of-bag (OOB) samples. Within this
242 framework, three samples from the case group and four samples from the control group were
243 misclassified. The OOB error rate is indicated as 0.113, as detailed in Supplementary Table
244 S1.

245 **3.3. Association of elemental content in breast milk with infant growth factors**

246 Using SPSS software, linear regression analysis was performed to determine the relationship
247 between identified elements and the early growth pattern of infants, both with and without
248 adjustment for confounders. In this analysis, growth patterns (HAZ, WAZ, WHZ scores) served
249 as dependent variables, while identified elements were considered independent variables. Only
250 elements with a p-value < 0.05 were included in Table 3a-3c.

251 Initially, results without confounder adjustment were presented. Notably, a one-unit increase
252 in the As level (Table 3a) corresponded to a decrease of 2.949 in the child's WAZ score and
253 2.406 in the WHZ score (Table 3c). Notably, Mo was the only element displaying a positive
254 association with all calculated z scores, including WAZ, HAZ, and, WHZ with the values of
255 1.503, 1.179, and 1.315, respectively as shown in Table 3a-3c.

256 Subsequently, birth weight, gestational age, and age at the time of sample collection which
257 might act as confounders in this association, were adjusted in the analysis due to their
258 significance in Table 1. As showed significance in the model with WHZ, suggesting its
259 potential impact on growth in this specific context. Moreover, Mo demonstrated marginal
260 significance in the models with WAZ and HAZ. It is noteworthy that Mo did not sustain in the
261 adjusted models, indicating a potential confounding effect of birth weight, gestational age, and
262 age at the time of sample collection on their association with early growth patterns.

263 **4. Discussion**

264
265 In the initial six months of a child's life, breast milk serves as the sole source of essential
266 nutrients and energy required for their development, offering protection against chronic
267 diseases and infections. Despite these benefits, the well-being of an infant can be compromised
268 by the presence of toxic substances, including metals, in the breast milk of mothers. Infants are
269 more vulnerable to environmental contaminants compared to adults, as certain protective
270 mechanisms such as the plasma protein binding capacity, enzymatic elimination processes in
271 the liver and kidneys, blood-brain barrier and immune systems are still underdeveloped in early
272 infancy [17]. In our study, we aimed to investigate the relationship between metal
273 concentrations in breast milk and child growth outcomes. Our findings suggest associations
274 between specific metals and child z scores; however, it is important to interpret these results
275 with caution. Given the study design and the limited exposure period, we cannot conclusively

276 determine the effects of metal exposure. Moreover, necessary adjustments for potential
277 confounders were made to highlight associations, but further research with extended exposure
278 periods is required to better understand these relationships.

279 Among the toxic elements, As is recognized as a potent toxicant and carcinogen. Prenatal
280 exposure to As has been investigated for its correlation with negative pregnancy outcomes,
281 such as spontaneous abortions, stillbirths, low birth weight, and infant mortality [18].
282 Additionally, the association between As exposure and preterm birth [19] along with
283 respiratory infections and diarrhea during infancy and childhood [20] have been assessed. In
284 this case-control study, we observed the consequences of increased As levels in maternal milk
285 on child anthropometry. Our findings revealed a decrease in both WAZ and WHZ scores.
286 Maternal As exposure could be associated with the consumption of drinking water, as it has
287 been reported that the groundwater As concentration in this region has escalated to 1100 µg/L,
288 significantly exceeding both the international WHO limit of 10 µg/L and locally set threshold
289 of 50 µg/L [21].

290 After arsenic, Pb is the second most toxic element, existing in both organic and inorganic
291 forms. However, in the environment, inorganic Pb predominates. A positive correlation
292 between Pb concentrations in human milk and water consumption has been reported [22].
293 Additionally, a study conducted in Pakistan's Sindh region revealed poor water quality, with
294 Pb concentrations surpassing health standards [23]. Excessive exposure to Pb can lead to
295 dysfunction in the nervous, digestive, and immunological systems [24]. In line with the
296 previously reported study on water quality in this region, the observed elevated levels of Pb in
297 the case group could be strongly associated with the consumption of unsafe water by mothers
298 during and after pregnancy.

299 Moreover, the case group exhibited higher levels of Mn and Ba compared to the control group.
300 The consumption of contaminated water with high levels of Mn [25] and Ba [26] has toxic

301 effects. While Mn is essential for proper fetal growth and development, excess amounts have
302 been reported to cause neurotoxicity, categorizing it as a brain drainer among environmental
303 agents [27]. It's important to note that Mn absorption is age-dependent; infants especially
304 premature ones retain a greater proportion of Mn than adults [28]. The lower threshold aligns
305 with the US EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency) recommendation that
306 infants under six months should not be exposed to water with Mn concentrations exceeding
307 300 µg/L for more than ten days annually [29]. However, a previous study conducted in that
308 region observed Mn concentrations in groundwater exceeding the WHO recommended limit
309 of 400 µg/L [30].

310 On the other hand, Ba contamination is associated with congenital defects in newborns, as
311 indicated in various studies [31]. Prenatal exposure measured through Ba levels in pregnant
312 women's hair correlates strongly with an increased risk of heart [32] and neural tube defects
313 [33] in their offspring. Therefore, particular attention is needed for the decontamination of
314 water consumed by pregnant mothers and infants in their developmental stages to protect them
315 from long-term detrimental effects.

316 Furthermore, two other elements were found to be elevated in the control group compared to
317 the case group, including Mo and Se. Mo, an essential trace element in the human diet, acts as
318 a cofactor for several enzymes involved in substance breakdown. Its role is crucial for
319 sustaining and nurturing the strength and overall well-being of both bones and the nervous
320 system [34]. Primary dietary sources of Mo include leafy vegetables, grains, legumes, meat,
321 eggs, and cow's milk. In infants, human milk or formula milk serves as the main source of Mo
322 before weaning. In a prior reported study, the levels of Mo were found to be higher in formula
323 milk intended for full-term or premature infants than in human milk [35]. Simultaneously, it
324 has shown a positive association with both the HAZ and WHZ scores of children and was found

325 in higher concentrations in the milk samples of mothers who belonged to the control group
326 compared to cases. This underscores its significance in the early growth of infants.

327 Another essential micronutrient for life is Se, crucial for as its presence in breast milk is vital
328 [36]. Deficiencies have been linked to obstetric complications such as preterm delivery,
329 spontaneous abortion, gestational diabetes, and intrauterine growth restriction [37].
330 Selenoprotein P, the primary carrier of Se in plasma has a preference for retaining Se in the
331 brain over other organs. A study by Hoova *et.al.* revealed substantial quantities of selenoprotein
332 P in breast milk, confirming breastfeeding as an outstanding source of Se for newborns. The
333 order of selenoprotein P concentration was found highest in maternal serum, followed by cord
334 serum and breast milk [38]. An increased level of this micronutrient was observed in the control
335 group, a finding consistent with previous studies that highlight its role in child health. However,
336 excess levels of these essential micronutrients can be harmful to health.

337 A limitation of this study is the lack of information regarding both the dietary habits of the
338 mothers and their working status. These factors could have an impact on the milk intake of
339 their infants. Additionally, it is important to recognize that the observed outcomes may be
340 influenced by prolonged exposure to toxicants. For future investigations, a comprehensive study
341 with a larger sample size that compares corresponding maternal serum samples with breast
342 milk samples could provide enhanced insights into elemental exposure levels for both mothers
343 and their breastfed infants.

344 **5. Conclusions**

345 In conclusion, this study the first of its kind in the South region of Pakistan sheds light on the
346 elemental composition of breast milk and its potential impact on infant health. Elevated
347 concentrations of toxic elements such as As and Pb in the case group underscore the urgent
348 need for action from higher authorities in the health sector. The findings highlight the critical
349 role of breast milk as a source of both essential and potentially harmful elements. Despite these

350 concerns, promoting breastfeeding is crucial as there is no other substitute for a newborn.
351 Ensuring the well-being of infants requires focused attention on the region's drinking water and
352 food sources.

353

354 **Declarations**

355 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

356 This study was approved by the Department of Pediatrics and Child Health at Aga Khan
357 University, while informed consent was received from all subjects. The Ethical Review
358 Committee at AKU (3836-Ped-ERC-15) and the Independent Ethics Committee of the
359 International Center for Chemical and Biological Sciences approved the experimental protocol
360 (ICCBS/IEC-065-HB-HM-2021/Protocol/1.0I).

361

362 **Consent for publication**

363 Not applicable

364

365 **Availability of data and materials**

366 The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the
367 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

368

369 **Competing interests**

370 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

371

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377

378 **Authors' contributions**

379 **Prof Syed Ghulam Musharraf** conceptualization, supervision, resources, writing- review and
380 editing.

381 **Nurmeen Adil** investigation, methodology, software, validation, data curation, writing-
382 original draft.

383 **Syed Sibte-Hassan** investigation, methodology, software, data curation, writing-review and
384 editing.

385 **Dr. Amna Jabbar Siddiqui** validation, writing – review and editing.

386 **Drs Zehra Jamil and Junaid Iqbal** resources, data curation.

387 **Syed Asad Ali** resources, funding acquisition.

388 All authors approved the final manuscript as submitted and agreed to be accountable for all
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489 **Table 1:** Clinical characteristics of both human breast milk (HBM) groups (cases and controls).

Variable	Statistics	HBM case group (samples collected from mothers of undernourished children)	HBM control group (samples collected from mothers of nourished children)	<i>p</i> -value
Birth weight (kg)	Mean ± SD	2.59 ± 0.39	2.97 ± 0.44	0.002
Gender	N			0.445
	M	22	10	
	F	20	10	
Gestational age (weeks)	Mean ± SD	38.07 ± 1.69	38.95 ± 0.22	0.002
Age at the time of sample collection (months)	Mean ± SD	4 ± 1.13	5 ± 0.78	3.43 E-05
HAZ at the time of sample collection	Mean ± SD	-2.04 ± 1.42	-0.68 ± 1.01	7.08 E-05
WAZ at the time of sample collection	Mean ± SD	-3.59 ± 1.38	0.02 ± 1.00	7.44 E-16
WHZ at the time of sample collection	Mean ± SD	-2.85 ± 0.73	0.67 ± 1.07	1.26 E-13
Runny nose (episodes per 6 months)	Mean ± SD	12 ± 8.62	14 ± 10.89	0.414
Wheezing (episodes per 6 months)	Mean ± SD	4 ± 7.63	2 ± 3.11	0.068
Diarrhea (episodes per 6 months)	Mean ± SD	3.97 ± 5.64	4 ± 7.22	0.990
Vomiting (episodes per 6 months)	Mean ± SD	2 ± 4.27	1.78 ± 4.68	0.809
Fever (episodes per 6 months)	Mean ± SD	12 ± 9.61	14 ± 7.66	0.433
6 months' biomarker profile: Glucagon-Like Peptide-1 (GLP) (pg/mL) Leptin (pg/mL) Alpha-1 Acid Glycoprotein (AGP) (mg/L) Ferritin (ng/mL) C-reactive Protein (CRP) (mg/L) Insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) (ng/mL)	Mean ± SD	1339 ± 1268.32 181 ± 142.12 109 ± 75.69 159 ± 137.70 0 ± 2.06 23 ± 14.37	1211 ± 590.69 384 ± 127.60 103 ± 50.17 95 ± 204.24 0 ± 0.48 39 ± 23.53	0.589 1.31 E-06 0.724 0.215 0.225 0.010
Rota Vaccine Status	Responder (N)	20	10	1.000

Maternal age (years)	Mean ± SD	23.83 ± 1.08	24.00 ± 0.00	0.323
Maternal weight (kg)	Mean ± SD	43.78 ± 15.16	44.36 ± 16.25	0.895
Maternal height (cm)	Mean ± SD	149 ± 24.03	139 ± 47.85	0.410
Maternal BMI (kg/m ²)	Mean ± SD	19 ± 5.79	20 ± 2.24	0.241

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492 **Table 2:** Significantly altered marker elements between two groups based on t-test analysis.

S.No.	Elements	FC	log ₂ (FC)	p-value
1	As	18.917	4.242	0.002
2	Pb	2.889	1.530	0.036
3	Mn	2.933	1.552	0.024
4	Ba	5.325	2.413	0.019
5	Se	0.190	-2.392	0.000
6	Mo	0.204	-2.293	0.024

493 S. No. = Serial Number

494 FC = Fold Change

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496 **Table 3:** Linear regression analysis between independent variables (marker elements) and
 497 dependent variables (growth patterns i.e. HAZ, WAZ, and WHZ).

a. Dependent Variable: Weight-for-age z-score (WAZ)			
S.No.	Elements	B-coefficient	p-value
1	As	-2.949	9E-08
2	Mo	1.503	0.008
b. Dependent Variable: height-for-age z-score (HAZ)			
S.No.	Elements	B-coefficient	p-value
1	Mo	1.179	0.020
c. Dependent Variable: Weight-for-height z-score (WHZ)			
S.No.	Elements	B-coefficient	p-value
1	As	-2.406	5E-07
2	Mo	1.315	0.008

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504 **Figure 1:** PCA findings (A) 2D scores plot between PC1 and PC2. (B) In the scree plot, the
505 green line represents the accumulated variance explained, while the blue one shows the
506 variance explained by individual PCs.

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511 **Figure 2:** PLS-DA analysis. (A) 2D score plot illustrating components 1 and 2. (B) Bar plots
 512 display three performance measures (prediction accuracy, R2, and Q2) across varying
 513 component numbers. The red '*' highlights optimal values based on the chosen Q2 measure.
 514 (C) Histogram summarizing the results of permutation tests.
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Figure 3: Box plot for discriminatory marker elements, identify the differences in case and control group. Normalized intensities are presented in the y-axis.

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541 **Figure 4:** Hierarchical cluster analysis result shown as (A) Dendrogram. (B) Heatmap of

542 significant elements between two groups.

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